

APPENDIX

A. Detailed Models of Distributed Energy Resources

This paper considers three typical kinds of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs): Energy Storage Systems (ESSs), Thermal Controllable Residents (TCRs), and Deferrable Loads (DLs). For detailed derivations and explanations of the DER models, please refer to [9].

1) *Energy Storage Systems*: Considering the charging and discharging schedule along with the state-of-charge limits, the ESS model can be represented as follows:

$$0 \leq P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,in} \leq \bar{P}_{i,k}^{ESS,in}, \forall t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{ESS,end} \quad (22.a)$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,out} \leq \bar{P}_{i,k}^{ESS,out}, \forall t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{ESS,end} \quad (22.b)$$

$$-\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{ESS} \leq \left\{ P_{i,k,t-1}^{ESS,in} - P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,in}, P_{i,k,t-1}^{ESS,out} - P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,out} \right\} \leq \bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{ESS} \quad (22.c)$$

$$, \forall t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{ESS,end}$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{ESS} = \theta_{i,k}^{ESS} E_{i,k,t-1}^{ESS} + \left(\kappa_{i,k}^{ESS,in} P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,in} - P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,out} / \kappa_{i,k}^{ESS,out} \right) \Delta t \quad (22.d)$$

$$, \forall t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{ESS,end}$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{ESS} \leq E_{i,k,t}^{ESS} \leq \bar{E}_{i,k}^{ESS}, \forall t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{ESS,end} \quad (22.e)$$

where $P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,in}$, $P_{i,k,t}^{ESS,out}$, and $E_{i,k,t}^{ESS}$ are the charging power, discharging power and storage energy, respectively; $\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{ESS}$ is the ramping limit; $\theta_{i,k}^{ESS}$ is the energy dissipation rate; $\bar{P}_{i,k}^{ESS,in} / \bar{P}_{i,k}^{ESS,out}$ is the maximum charging/ discharging power; $\bar{E}_{i,k}^{ESS} / \underline{E}_{i,k}^{ESS}$ is the maximum/ minimum storage energy constrained by the state-of-charge; $\kappa_{i,k}^{ESS,in} / \kappa_{i,k}^{ESS,out}$ is the efficiency of charging/ discharging power; $t_{i,k}^{ESS,stt} / t_{i,k}^{ESS,end}$ is the start/end available period.

2) *Thermal Controllable Residents*: Accounting for thermal inertia, the dynamic characteristics of TCRs can be represented by a derivative function, which is then converted into the following discrete form:

$$P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,in} \leq P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,in} \leq \bar{P}_{i,k}^{TCR,in}, \forall t_{i,k}^{TCR,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{TCR,end} \quad (23.a)$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{TCR} \leq E_{i,k,t}^{TCR} \leq \bar{E}_{i,k}^{TCR}, \forall t_{i,k}^{TCR,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{TCR,end} \quad (23.b)$$

$$-\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{TCR} \leq \left\{ P_{i,k,t-1}^{TCR,in} - P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,in}, P_{i,k,t-1}^{TCR,out} - P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,out} \right\} \leq \bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{TCR} \quad (23.c)$$

$$, \forall t_{i,k}^{TCR,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{TCR,end}$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{TCR} = \theta_{i,k}^{TCR} E_{i,k,t-1}^{TCR} + \eta_{i,k}^{TCR} P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,in} \Delta t + \omega_{i,k}^{TCR} w_{i,k,t}^{TCR} \quad (23.d)$$

$$, \forall t_{i,k}^{TCR,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{TCR,end}$$

where $P_{i,k,t}^{TCR,in}$, and $E_{i,k,t}^{TCR}$ are the power consumption and indoor temperature, respectively; $\bar{P}_{i,k}^{TCR,in} / \underline{P}_{i,k}^{TCR,in}$ is the maximum/ minimum power consumption; $\bar{E}_{i,k}^{TCR} / \underline{E}_{i,k}^{TCR}$ is the upper/ lower bound of the expected indoor temperature; $\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{TCR}$ is the ramping limit; $w_{i,k,t}^{TCR}$ is the ambient temperature; $\theta_{i,k}^{TCR}$ is the dissipation rate; $\eta_{i,k}^{TCR}$ is the conversion coefficient from the active power to temperature; $\omega_{i,k}^{TCR} = 1 - \theta_{i,k}^{TCR}$ is the impact factor of ambient temperature; $t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} / t_{i,k}^{DL,end}$ is the start/end available period.

3) *Deferrable Loads*: The charging load of plug-in electric vehicles (EVs) is a common example of DLs. This type of DER

must meet its energy requirement within a specified available timeframe, which can be expressed as follows:

$$P_{i,k}^{DL,in} \leq P_{i,k,t}^{DL,in} \leq \bar{P}_{i,k}^{DL,in}, \forall t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{DL,end} \quad (24.a)$$

$$0 \leq E_{i,k,t}^{DL} \leq \bar{E}_{i,k}^{DL}, \forall t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{DL,end} \quad (24.b)$$

$$-\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{DL} \leq \left\{ P_{i,k,t-1}^{DL,in} - P_{i,k,t}^{DL,in}, P_{i,k,t-1}^{DL,out} - P_{i,k,t}^{DL,out} \right\} \leq \bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{DL} \quad (24.c)$$

$$, \forall t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{DL,end}$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{DL} = \theta_{i,k}^{DL} E_{i,k,t-1}^{DL} + \eta_{i,k}^{DL} P_{i,k,t}^{DL} \Delta t, \forall t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} \leq t \leq t_{i,k}^{DL,end} \quad (24.d)$$

$$E_{i,k,t}^{DL} \geq E_{i,k,t}^{DL,rqr}, \text{ for } t = t_{i,k}^{DL,end} \quad (24.e)$$

where $P_{i,k,t}^{DL,in}$, and $E_{i,k,t}^{DL}$ are the electric power input and residual energy, respectively; $\bar{P}_{i,k}^{DL,in} / \underline{P}_{i,k}^{DL,in}$ is the maximum/ minimum charging power; $\bar{E}_{i,k}^{DL}$ is the rated energy capacity; $\bar{\delta}_{i,k}^{DL}$ is the ramping limit; $\theta_{i,k}^{DL}$ is the dissipation rate; $\eta_{i,k}^{DL}$ is the conversion coefficient; $E_{i,k}^{DL,rqr}$ is the charging energy requirement; $t_{i,k}^{DL,stt} / t_{i,k}^{DL,end}$ is the start/end available period.

B. Derivation of DER Coefficient Matrices

The derivation of the coefficient matrix involves two key steps. First, QR decomposition and Gaussian elimination are used to remove equality constraints, eliminating the variables $P_{i,k,t}^{DER,in}$ and $P_{i,k,t}^{DER,out}$. Next, Fourier-Motzkin Elimination (FME) and redundancy identification techniques are applied to remove inequality constraints, eliminating the variable $E_{i,k,t}^{DER}$ and leaving only the inequality constraints in terms of $P_{i,k,t}^{DER}$.

1) *Dealing with Equality Constraints*: The equality constraints (1.e)-(1.f) are first recast into the following compact form, where $\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{eq} / \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{eq}$ is the known coefficient matrix/vector.

$$\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{eq} \left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,in}; \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,out}; \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER}; \mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER} \right] = \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{eq} \quad (25.a)$$

The QR decomposition is applied to factorize $\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{eq}$, yielding (25.b)-(25.c), where $\mathbf{Q}_{i,k}^{eq}$ is an orthogonal matrix and $\mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,1}$ is an invertible upper triangular matrix:

$$\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{eq} = \mathbf{Q}_{i,k}^{eq} \left[\mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,1}; \mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,2} \right] \quad (25.b)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,1} \left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,in}; \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,out} \right] + \mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,2} \left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER}; \mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER} \right] = \left(\mathbf{Q}_{i,k}^{eq} \right)^T \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{eq} \Rightarrow \quad (25.c)$$

$$\left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,in}; \mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,out} \right] = \left(\mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,1} \right)^{-1} \left(\left(\mathbf{Q}_{i,k}^{eq} \right)^T \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{eq} - \mathbf{R}_{i,k}^{eq,2} \left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER}; \mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER} \right] \right)$$

Next, we apply Gaussian elimination to substitute equation (25.c) into constraints (1.a)-(1.b), thereby eliminating the variables $\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,in}$ and $\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER,out}$. We can then recast the original set (1) into the following full-dimensional set $\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{DER}$, characterized by linear inequalities that involve only the variables $\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER}$ and $\mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER}$ where $\mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{eq} / \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{eq}$ is the known coefficient matrix/vector.

$$\mathbb{U}_{i,k}^{DER} = \left\{ \mathbf{H}_{i,k}^{ineq} \left[\mathbf{P}_{i,k}^{DER}; \mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER} \right] \leq \mathbf{h}_{i,k}^{ineq} \right\} \quad (25.d)$$

2) *Dealing with Inequality Constraints*: The approach outlined in [13] is employed to combine Fourier-Motzkin Elimination (FME) and redundancy constraint identification techniques for eliminating extraneous variables $\mathbf{E}_{i,k}^{DER}$ in (25.d).

The key strategy involves first using FME to remove a target variable, followed by applying redundancy identification to eliminate any redundant constraints in the resulting set. This process is iteratively continued to remove the next variable until all extraneous variables are eliminated. Finally, the original DER set (1) can be recast as the full-dimensional and non-redundant set (2).

Indeed, FME has been criticized for its exponential complexity, primarily because redundant constraints accumulate during the process. However, we emphasize that the combined approach of FME and redundancy constraint identification remains highly applicable to the DER models in this paper for two main reasons: first, as noted in reference [13], embedding redundancy constraint identification at each step of the FME process can effectively reduce its complexity; second, and more importantly, the DER model presented in this paper allows for parallel elimination, as each DER model operates independently. Therefore, the complexity of FME does not significantly increase with the scale of DERs.

C. Proof of the Proposition 3

The set inclusion $\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbb{U}_i^{base} \subseteq \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbb{P}_i^{aff}$ holds if and only if for any direction $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N^T}$, (26.a) holds:

$$\max_{\mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base}} \mathbf{c}^T (\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg}) \leq \max_{\mathbf{P}_i^{aff} \in \mathbb{P}_i^{aff}} \mathbf{c}^T \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{aff} \quad (26.a)$$

From the strong duality of linear programs, we can recast the right-hand side of (26.a) as its dual form as shown in (26.b):

$$\max_{\mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base}} \mathbf{c}^T (\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg}) \leq \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\text{row}(\Gamma_i^{aff})}} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{h}_i^{aff} \quad (26.b)$$

Since the minimum of the right-hand side set is higher than the maximum of the left-hand side set, it indicates that every element in the right-hand side set is greater than those in the left-hand side set. Thus, the following relation holds for $\forall \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N^T}$, $\forall \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\text{row}(\Gamma_i^{aff})}$, $\mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} = \mathbf{c}^T \Gamma_i^{aff}$, $\forall \mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base}$:

$$\mathbf{c}^T (\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg}) \leq \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{h}_i^{aff} \quad (26.c)$$

Next, we prove the existence of (13.a) and (13.b) individually.

1) *Proof of (13.a)*: Since $\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbb{U}_i^{base} \subseteq \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbb{P}_i^{aff}$, there exists $\mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base}$ and $\mathbf{P}_i^{aff,0} \in \mathbb{P}_i^{aff}$ such that:

$$\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} = \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{aff,0} \quad (26.d)$$

Since \mathbb{U}_i^{base} is full-dimensional, there exists $\epsilon_i \geq 0$, and a N^T -dimensional unit box \mathbb{B}_i such that $\mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} + \epsilon_i \mathbb{B}_i \subset \mathbb{U}_i^{base}$ holds [30]. Further, we can derive:

$$\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} (\mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} + \epsilon_i \mathbb{B}_i) \subset \mathbb{P}_i^{aff} \quad (26.e)$$

Thus, there exists $\boldsymbol{\psi}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N_i^{AP,total}}$ such that:

$$\gamma_i^{agg} + \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} (\mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} + \epsilon_i \mathbf{e}_i) = \Gamma_i^{aff} (\mathbf{P}_i^{aff} + \boldsymbol{\psi}_i) \quad (26.f)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i is the unit vector in the Cartesian directions.

Thus, we have $\Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{e}_i = \Gamma_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\psi}_i$, implying that $\Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \in \text{range}(\Gamma_i^{aff})$. Here, given matrix \mathbf{A} , we denote $\text{range}(\mathbf{A})$ as its column-space. Then, we denote the space transformation matrix as $\mathbf{G}_i^{aux} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_i^{AP,total} \times N^T}$, thereby deriving $\Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} = \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbf{G}_i^{aux}$.

Also, we have $-\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i^{agg} = \Gamma_i^{agg} \mathbf{I}_i^{agg} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg,0} - \Gamma_i^{aff} \mathbf{P}_i^{aff}$, implying that $-\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i^{agg} \in \text{range}(\Gamma_i^{aff})$. Then, we denote the space transformation matrix as $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_i^{AP,total}}$, thereby deriving $-\boldsymbol{\gamma}_i^{agg} = \Gamma_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux}$.

This completes the proof of (13.a).

2) *Proof of (13.b)*: According to (13.a), and $\mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} = \mathbf{c}^T \Gamma_i^{aff}$ in (26.b), we can recast (26.c) as:

$$\mathbf{u}^T (\mathbf{h}_i^{aff} + \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux} - \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \mathbf{G}_i^{aux} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg}) \geq 0 \quad (26.g)$$

To efficiently find the minimum in (26.g), we provide a conservative approximation by dropping constraint $\mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} = \mathbf{c}^T \Gamma_i^{aff}$. Then, \mathbf{u} is only constrained to be non-negative, implying that $\mathbf{h}_i^{aff} + \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux} - \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \mathbf{G}_i^{aux} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \geq 0$, $\forall \mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \in \mathbb{U}_i^{base}$. Then, we form a polytope $\mathbb{Q}_i = \{\mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \in \mathbb{R}^{N^T} \mid \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \mathbf{G}_i^{aux} \mathbf{P}_i^{agg} \leq \mathbf{h}_i^{aff} + \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux}\}$, implying that $\mathbb{Q}_i \subseteq \mathbb{P}_i^{agg}$. According to [31], the polytope containment relationship, i.e., $\mathbb{Q}_i \subseteq \mathbb{P}_i^{agg}$, holds if there exists a auxiliary variable matrix $\mathbf{A}_i^{aux} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\text{row}(\mathbf{H}_i^{aff}) \times \text{row}(\mathbf{H}_i^{base})}$ such that $\mathbf{A}_i^{aux} \mathbf{H}_i^{base} = \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \mathbf{G}_i^{aux}$, $\mathbf{A}_i^{aux} \mathbf{h}_i^{base} \leq \mathbf{h}_i^{aff} + \mathbf{H}_i^{aff} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{aux}$.

This completes the proof of (13.b). \blacksquare

D. Parameters in Case Studies

Fig. 11. Load demand and wind power profiles in a typical day.

TABLE VI
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF ESS CLUSTERS
IN 6-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Energy capacity (kWh)	TGD	50	10	20	80
Max. charging/discharging power (kW)	TGD	12.5	6.5	3.2	25
Initial energy (kWh)	TGD	10	4.5	2	15.5
Energy dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.98	1.0
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	15
End available time	UD	--	--	14	24

*TGD: truncated Gaussian distributions. UD: uniformly distributed.

TABLE VII
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF PLUG-IN EV
CLUSTERS IN 6-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Energy requirement (kWh)	TGD	40	10	20	50
Max. charging power (kW)	TGD	12	6.5	5	20
Initial energy (kWh)	TGD	15	5	6	35
Energy dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.98	1.0
Conversion coefficient (kWh/kW)	UD	--	--	0.9	1.0
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	12

End available time	UD	--	--	12	24
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TABLE VIII
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF TCR CLUSTERS
IN 6-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Max. indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	24	0.5	22.5	25.5
Min. indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	19	0.5	20.5	17.5
Initial indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	21	0.3	20	22
Max power consumption (kW)	TGD	30	5	20	40
Temperature dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.94	0.98
Conversion coefficient (kWh/kW)	UD	--	--	0.08	0.10
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	16
End available time	UD	--	--	12	24

TABLE IX
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF ESS CLUSTERS
IN 118-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Energy capacity (kWh)	TGD	50	15	20	90
Max. charging/discharging power (kW)	TGD	10	7	5	25
Initial energy (kWh)	TGD	15	6	5	25
Energy dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.98	1.0
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	16
End available time	UD	--	--	9	24

TABLE X
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF PLUG-IN EV
CLUSTERS IN 118-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Energy requirement (kWh)	TGD	40	10	20	60
Max. charging power (kW)	TGD	15	8	7	23
Initial energy (kWh)	TGD	20	6	5	35
Energy dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.97	1.0
Conversion coefficient (kWh/kW)	UD	--	--	0.88	1.0
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	18
End available time	UD	--	--	10	24

TABLE XI
PARAMETER PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION OF TCR CLUSTERS
IN 118-BUS SYSTEM

Parameters	Distr.	Mean	Deviation	Min	Max
Max. indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	24	1	22	26
Min. indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	19	1	21	17
Initial indoor temperature (°C)	TGD	21	0.5	20	22
Max power consumption (kW)	TGD	30	5	20	40
Temperature dissipation rate (p.u.)	UD	--	--	0.94	0.98
Conversion coefficient (kWh/kW)	UD	--	--	0.08	0.10
Start available time	UD	--	--	1	17
End available time	UD	--	--	8	24